

Psychosomatic aspects of cardiovascular diseases

Aspectos psicossomáticos de las enfermedades cardiovasculares

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Received: 10/20/2024 Accepted: 01/19/2025 Published: 02/12/2025 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14876747>

Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are one of the major causes of mortality worldwide. In recent decades, there has been considerable interest in the study of psychosomatic factors influencing the development and course of these diseases. Psychosomatic aspects of CVDs encompass the interaction of psychological, emotional and social factors with physiological processes in the body, which in turn may increase the risk of heart and vascular disease. This article reviews key psychosomatic factors such as stress, depression, anxiety, personality types, and the impact of social support and family relationships on heart health. Particular attention is given to the mechanisms by which emotional disorders may contribute to

the development of hypertension, coronary heart disease, heart attacks and strokes.

The authors also present modern approaches to the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases taking into account psychosomatic aspects, including psychotherapeutic interventions, relaxation techniques and stress management. The study of psychosomatic mechanisms of CVDs is important for the development of comprehensive treatment methods aimed at improving patients' quality of life and reducing morbidity.

Key words: psychosomatics, cardiovascular diseases, stress, depression, personality types, prevention, treatment, stress management.

Las enfermedades cardiovasculares (ECV) son una de las principales causas de mortalidad en todo el mundo. En las últimas décadas, ha habido un interés considerable en el estudio de los factores psicosomáticos que influyen en el desarrollo y la evolución de estas enfermedades. Los aspectos psicosomáticos de las ECV abarcan la interacción de factores psicológicos, emocionales y sociales con los procesos fisiológicos del cuerpo, que a su vez pueden aumentar el riesgo de enfermedades cardíacas y vasculares. Este artículo revisa los factores psicosomáticos clave como el estrés, la depresión, la ansiedad, los tipos de personalidad y el impacto del apoyo social y las relaciones familiares en la salud cardíaca. Se presta especial atención a los mecanismos por los cuales los trastornos emocionales pueden contribuir al desarrollo de hipertensión, enfermedad cardíaca coronaria, ataques cardíacos y accidentes cerebrovasculares.

Los autores también presentan enfoques modernos para la prevención y el tratamiento de las enfermedades cardiovasculares teniendo en cuenta los aspectos psicosomáticos, incluidas las intervenciones psicoterapéuticas, las técnicas de relajación y el manejo del estrés. El estudio de los mecanismos psicosomáticos de las ECV es importante para el desarrollo de métodos de tratamiento integrales destinados a mejorar la calidad de vida de los pacientes y reducir la morbilidad.

Palabras clave: psicosomática, enfermedades cardiovasculares, estrés, depresión, tipos de personalidad, prevención, tratamiento, manejo del estrés.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain a major cause of disability and mortality worldwide. According to the World Health Organisation, CVDs are responsible for a significant proportion of premature deaths, highlighting the need for a comprehensive approach to their prevention and treatment. In recent decades, interest in the role of psychosomatic factors in the development and course of cardiovascular diseases has increased significantly. Psychosomatic disorders such as chronic stress, depression and anxiety have been recognised as important catalysts of various pathologies of the cardiovascular system¹.

Researches show that a person's psychological state can significantly influence physiological processes related to the heart and blood vessels, increasing the body's susceptibility to diseases such as hypertension, ischaemic heart disease, heart attacks and strokes. Emotional disorders, negative experiences, and personality traits can cause chronic tension, which in turn contributes to cardiovascular dysfunction.

The aim of this article is to review the main psychosomatic factors influencing the development of CVD, to analyse the mechanisms of their impact and to consider current approaches to complex treatment and prevention taking into account the psychosomatic component. It is important to emphasise that in modern medical practice the treatment of heart diseases cannot be limited to pharmacological methods only. Psychological support, stress management and psychotherapeutic techniques become an integral part of complex therapy of patients with cardiovascular diseases.

Thus, understanding the psychosomatic aspects of CVD and taking these factors into account in the treatment of patients is necessary to improve the effectiveness of medical care and the quality of life of patients.

Various theoretical methods were used to study psychosomatic aspects of cardiovascular diseases, which reveal the relationship between psychological and physiological processes in the body. The importance of these methods lies in the fact that they allow a deeper understanding of how the emotional and mental state of a person affects the development and course of heart and vascular diseases.

Psychoanalysis, based on the work of Freud, allows the study of unconscious processes that may influence the development of psychosomatic diseases. According to psychoanalytic theory, repressed emotions and conflicts can manifest as physical symptoms, including cardiovascular disorders. This method helps to investigate the role of internal conflicts, repressed stress and anxiety in cardiovascular disease.

Humanistic psychology, in particular the theory of Carl Rogers and Abraham Maslow, views the individual as a whole. Cognitive behavioural therapy focuses on analysing and changing negative thought patterns and behavioural reactions that may contribute to the development of psychosomatic diseases. The above method explores how psychological factors such as anxiety, depression, perfectionism and catastrophising can affect cardiovascular health. The theory of cognitive-behavioural therapy offers mechanisms for working with cognitive and emotional disorders, which can significantly reduce the risk of developing CVD.

The systems approach examines the interaction of various factors affecting human health, including psychological, social and physiological aspects. In the context of cardiovascular disease, the systems approach emphasises the importance of the social aspect.

Hans Selye developed the stress theory, which focuses on how chronic stress can affect health, including the cardiovascular system. Stress theory explains the mechanisms by which stressful events lead to physiological changes in the body, such as increased blood pressure, inflammation, and cardiovascular dysfunction. The above theoretical framework helps to understand how psycho-emotional stress can influence the development of CVDs.

R. Lazarus proposed a theory that the perception of stress and ways of overcoming it (coping strategies) play a key role in the development of psychosomatic diseases. In the context of CVD, this model allows us to analyze how personality traits, perception of stress, and

ways of adapting to stressful situations influence the development and progression of cardiovascular diseases.

It is also important to consider theoretical approaches that examine a patient's cognitive and emotional responses to various life events. For example, the "psychological stress and illness" theory (Lazarus and Folkman) examines how the perception of stressors and coping with them affect somatic health, including heart health. This approach helps to better understand how certain emotional reactions, such as depression or aggression, may contribute to the development of chronic heart disease.

The applied approaches and models allowed us to investigate various aspects of psychosomatic influence on the cardiovascular system, and to develop more effective methods of diagnostics, prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases taking into account the psychological state of the patient.

Results

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) occupy the leading place among the causes of mortality and disability in the world, which makes them one of the most urgent medical problems. In recent decades, psychosomatic factors influencing the development and course of these diseases have attracted considerable attention of researchers². Psychosomatic disorders include psychological and emotional aspects that may play a crucial role in the onset and progression of cardiovascular diseases.

Modern researches confirm, that stress, depression, anxiety, and personality types can have a significant impact on heart and blood vessel function. For example, chronic stress can contribute to high blood pressure, impaired heart function, and increases the risk of coronary heart disease, heart attacks, and strokes. Emotional disorders, such as depression, are also associated with an increased likelihood of cardiovascular disease and a worse prognosis for patients suffering from these diseases³.

In addition, psychosomatic aspects of CVD include not only the influence of stress and emotions, but also social factors such as social isolation, unfavourable family relationships and work stress, which may increase the negative impact on cardiovascular health⁴. In this regard, it is necessary to consider the complex influence of various psychosomatic factors on the patient's health.

The importance of taking into account psychosomatic aspects in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases lies

in the need to integrate psychotherapeutic and psychosocial methods into traditional treatment. This allows not only to reduce physical symptoms, but also to improve the psychological state of patients, which, in turn, contributes to more successful recovery and prevention of cardiovascular diseases⁵.

Psychosomatic aspects of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) reflect the complex interaction of psychological, emotional and social factors with physiological processes in the body, which significantly affects the development and course of these diseases⁶. The psychological state of a person is directly related to the work of the cardiovascular system, and numerous studies show that stress, anxiety, depression, and character traits can be important predisposing factors for the development of various heart and vascular diseases.

Table 1. Key psychosomatic factors and their impact on cardiovascular health

Psychosomatic factor	Description	Impact on heart health
Stres	The body's response to external and internal threats, accompanied by the release of stress hormones (adrenaline, cortisol).	Chronic stress can cause an increase in blood pressure, palpitations, and contribute to the development of hypertension, coronary heart disease and heart attacks
Depression	An emotional disorder characterised by prolonged depressed mood, loss of interest in life and impaired daily activities.	Depression contributes to increased levels of inflammation in the body, which increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. It also impairs your ability to follow your doctor's recommendations and lead a healthy lifestyle.
Anxiety	An emotional state associated with constant worry and expectation of threat.	Chronic anxiety levels leads to increased stress, which can provoke rapid heartbeat, increased blood pressure and vascular dysfunction.
Personality types	Personality traits such as type A (aggressive, competitive) and type B (calm, relaxed).	Type A is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease due to emotional stress, while Type B is less susceptible to these risks.
Social support	Having supportive relationships with friends, family, colleagues.	Strong social support helps to reduce stress levels and helps to cope with life's challenges, which reduces the risk of developing CVDs.
Family relations	Quality of relationships within the family (harmony, support, conflicts).	Positive family relationships reduce stress levels, while chronic conflict or violence increases the risk of cardiovascular disease.

The above table summarises the main psychosomatic factors and their impact on cardiovascular health, emphasising the importance of psycho-emotional state for the prevention and treatment of CVDs.

Chronic stress, anxiety and depression are key elements of psychosomatic effects on cardiac health⁷. In response to stressful situations, the body activates "fight or flight" mechanisms accompanied by the release of stress hormones such as adrenaline and cortisol, which increase heart rate, increase blood pressure and cause vasoconstriction⁸. With constant stress, these reactions become chronic, which increases the load on the heart and may contribute to the development of hypertension, coronary heart disease and other diseases.

Social support plays an important role in maintaining psycho-emotional well-being and influences heart health. People who have strong social ties and supportive relationships with friends, family or colleagues have a lower risk of developing cardiovascular disease. Social support helps to reduce stress levels, promotes better coping with difficult life situations and increases overall body resilience⁹.

The quality of family relationships is important for a person's psycho-emotional well-being and therefore for their heart health. Negative family relationships, such as chronic conflict, violence or emotional isolation, can be sources of stress and anxiety, which increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. In turn, a supportive and harmonious family can be an important factor in protecting against stress and maintaining normal cardiovascular function¹⁰.

Different personality types (e.g. "type A" with its characteristic tendency to be competitive, aggressive and high stress) may be associated with an increased risk of CVD. People with such characteristics are more likely to experience emotional tension and stress, which leads to impaired blood circulation and increases the likelihood of heart disease¹¹.

Psychosomatic influences are based on mechanisms that link emotions and mental state to physiological processes. For example, chronic stress can cause vascular inflammation and increased levels of "bad" cholesterol (LDL), which favours the formation of atherosclerotic plaques and increases the likelihood of thrombosis. In addition, emotions such as anger and aggression can lead to an increase in adrenaline levels, which negatively affects blood vessels and heart muscle.

Thus, psychosomatic factors represent an important component in the development of cardiovascular disease, and their impact on health requires a comprehensive approach that includes both physical and psychoemotional treatment and prevention.

The psychological state of a person does have a profound effect on the physiological processes occurring in the body and can significantly increase susceptibility to various cardiovascular diseases¹². Emotional tension, chronic stress, depression and anxiety play a key role in the development and progression of heart and vascular disease. Let us consider how exactly psychoemotional factors affect the cardiovascular system and increase the risk of developing such diseases as hypertension, coronary heart disease, heart attacks and strokes.

Stress, anxiety and chronic emotional tension can lead to a constant activation of “fight or flight” mechanisms, accompanied by the release of stress hormones such as adrenaline and cortisol. These hormones cause an increase in heart rate and vasoconstriction, leading to increased blood pressure. Chronic stress, especially with prolonged exposure, can contribute to the development of hypertension as well as impaired blood pressure control, which in turn increases the risk of heart attacks and strokes¹³.

Coronary heart disease (CHD) is associated with impaired blood supply to the heart muscle, most often due to atherosclerosis, when plaques form in the arteries, preventing normal blood flow. Psychological stress contributes to the development of inflammatory processes in the body, increased levels of “bad” cholesterol (LDL) and accelerated formation of atherosclerotic plaques¹⁴. Stress also affects the blood clotting system, increasing the likelihood of blood clots. All this contributes to the development of CHD and increases the risk of heart attacks.

Myocardial infarction (heart attack) often results from the destruction of atherosclerotic plaques, leading to the formation of blood clots that block blood flow in the coronary arteries. Psycho-emotional disorders such as anger, aggression, anxiety or depression can lead to a sharp increase in adrenaline levels, which in turn increases the risk of blood clots and impairs blood flow. Emotional distress and stressful situations can cause acute heart disease such as heart attack¹⁵.

Stroke (cerebral circulation disorder) is also closely related to psycho-emotional factors. Chronic stress, depression and anxiety can increase blood pressure, impair blood vessel function and elasticity. This increases the risk of blood clots and stroke. In addition, stress can contribute to the development of arrhythmias such as atrial fibrillation, which also increases the likelihood of stroke, as arrhythmias risk the formation of blood clots in the heart that can travel to the brain¹⁶.

Thus, psychological state plays a crucial role in the development of cardiovascular diseases such as hypertension, ischaemic heart disease, heart attack and stroke. Chronic stress, anxiety, depression and other emotional disorders can disrupt physiological processes in the body, contributing to the deterioration of the cardiovascular system. This emphasises the importance of a comprehensive approach to the treatment and prevention of CVD, which includes not only medical but also psychotherapeutic methods aimed at managing stress and emotional state of the patient.

Emotional disorders, negative experiences and personality traits can indeed cause chronic tension in the body, which in turn contributes to dysfunction of the cardiovascular system. These factors affect both the physiological and psychological state of a person, disrupting the normal function of the heart and blood vessels. Let's consider how exactly emotional disorders and personality traits can affect the cardiovascular system.

Emotional disorders such as depression and anxiety are among the most important risk factors for cardiovascular disease. Chronic anxiety and depression lead to a sustained increase in stress levels, which activates the sympathetic nervous system and increases the level of stress hormones (adrenaline, cortisol). These hormones contribute to vasoconstriction, increased blood pressure and increased heart rate.

Emotional disturbances can cause arrhythmias (such as tachycardia or atrial fibrillation), which increases the risk of stroke or heart attack. Depression and anxiety are associated with increased levels of inflammation in the body, which can contribute to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques and damage to blood vessel walls, increasing the risk of diseases such as coronary heart disease¹⁷. Negative experiences such as anger, aggression, resentment or chronic irritability can have a strong impact on the cardiovascular system.

Emotions such as anger lead to a rapid release of adrenaline and other catecholamines, which increases heart rate, raises blood pressure and promotes vasoconstriction. These effects can exacerbate pre-existing cardiovascular problems¹⁸.

Studies show that chronic anger and aggression may be associated with an increased risk of hypertension, heart attacks and strokes because these emotions increase the workload on the heart. Personality type also plays an important role in the occurrence of chronic tension and its effects on the cardiovascular system. People with personality type A, who are highly competitive, aggressive, success-seeking and prone to stress, have an increased risk of cardiovascular disease. They often experience stress, which increases levels of stress hormones, accelerates vascular aging and can lead to heart disease. People with personality type B, on the other hand, are more calm and relaxed, which contrib-

utes to lower stress levels and healthier heart and blood vessels. People with personality type C tend to suppress emotions, especially anger and aggression. They may not express their feelings, which leads to chronic inner tension and, as a consequence, an increased risk of cardiovascular disease¹⁹.

Chronic stress caused by emotional disorders or personality traits can lead to the following physiological consequences: chronic stress and emotional stress can impair the function of the endothelium, which regulates vascular tone, which contributes to the development of atherosclerosis and other vascular diseases; chronic stress and emotional disorders increase inflammation in the body, which negatively affects the heart and blood vessels. This can lead to damage to vascular walls and accelerated development of atherosclerosis; chronic stress and negative emotions increase the likelihood of blood clots in the vascular system, which can lead to heart attack or stroke²⁰.

Emotional disturbances, negative experiences and personality traits play a key role in the development of chronic tension, which has a significant impact on cardiovascular health. Increased stress can lead to an increased risk of hypertension, coronary heart disease, heart attacks and strokes²¹. Understanding the relationship between psychological well-being and physical health is an important step in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular disease, which emphasises the need for a comprehensive approach that includes psychotherapeutic support alongside medical treatment.

Emotional disorders such as stress, depression, anxiety, anger and aggression can significantly affect physiological processes by disrupting the normal functioning of the cardiovascular system. These disorders affect the body through various mechanisms that can contribute to the development of hypertension, coronary heart disease (CHD), heart attacks and strokes.

Emotional disorders cause activation of the sympathetic nervous system (SNS), which controls the body's responses to stressful situations. Stress, anxiety, anger and depression lead to the release of the stress hormones adrenaline and cortisol²².

Adrenaline increases heart rate, causes vasoconstriction and increases blood pressure. This leads to increased stress on the heart and blood vessels, which can cause hypertension and accelerate the development of atherosclerosis.

Cortisol stimulates the process of inflammation in the body, which favours the formation of atherosclerotic plaques on the walls of arteries. In turn, this increases the risk of heart attacks, strokes and other cardiovascular diseases. Emotional disorders such as depression, anxiety and chronic stress contribute to increased levels of inflammation in the body. Inflammation plays a key role

in the development of atherosclerosis, a process in which fatty deposits (plaques) form in the walls of arteries, which can narrow vessels and prevent normal blood flow.

Inflammation causes damage to the endothelium (the inner lining of blood vessels), which accelerates the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. It can also lead to the formation of blood clots, as damaged endothelium causes activation of the blood clotting mechanism. Emotional disorders can disrupt the normal function of the endothelium, the cells lining the inside of blood vessels. Under the influence of chronic stress and depression reduces the production of nitric oxide, which is necessary for the relaxation of blood vessels. This leads to vasoconstriction and increased vascular permeability: due to nitric oxide deficiency, vessels become less elastic, which increases the risk of hypertension and reduces blood supply to organs, and fatty particles and inflammatory cells deposit on vessel walls, which increases the risk of atherosclerosis.

Emotional disorders can affect the haemostasis (blood clotting) system by increasing its coagulation. This is due to an increase in platelet levels and the activity of some clotting factors such as fibrinogen²³. Increased clotting favours the formation of blood clots in blood vessels, which can block blood flow and lead to myocardial infarction or stroke if the clot blocks the coronary arteries or brain vessels.

Chronic stress and depression can affect blood lipid levels, especially by increasing levels of "bad" cholesterol (LDL) and decreasing levels of "good" cholesterol (HDL). High LDL levels promote the formation of atherosclerotic plaques, which can lead to coronary heart disease (CHD), heart attacks and strokes. Low HDL reduces the body's ability to clear excess cholesterol from the blood vessels, accelerating the process of atherosclerosis.

Emotional disorders such as depression can lead to decreased physical activity and poorer eating habits, which in turn can increase the risk of cardiovascular disease. People who suffer from depression or chronic stress are often prone to:

- Overeating (especially high-fat and high-sugar foods), which can lead to obesity and high cholesterol.
- Reduced physical activity, which impairs cardiovascular function and contributes to hypertension, diabetes and other diseases.

Chronic emotional disorders can also cause epigenetic changes that affect the expression of genes associated with cardiovascular disease. These changes can be passed down through several generations, increasing susceptibility to heart and vascular disease.

Emotional disorders play an important role in the development of hypertension, ischaemic heart disease, heart attacks and strokes, affecting the body through

a number of mechanisms: activation of the sympathetic nervous system, inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, changes in lipid metabolism, increased blood coagulation and decreased physical activity. All these mechanisms increase the burden on the cardiovascular system, contributing to the development of heart and vascular disease. This emphasises the importance of psycho-emotional health and the need for an integrated approach to the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases.

Modern approaches to the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) take into account not only traditional medical methods, but also psychosomatic aspects that have a significant impact on the development and course of these diseases. The psychological state of a person plays an important role in the functioning of the cardiovascular system, and many methods of treatment and prevention of CVD now include psychotherapeutic interventions, relaxation techniques and stress management.

Psychotherapy is aimed at reducing stress levels, anxiety, depression and other emotional disorders that can exacerbate cardiovascular disease. Cognitive behavioural therapy is used to change negative thoughts and behaviours that can contribute to stress and poor health. CBT helps patients.

Psychoanalysis and depth psychotherapy aim to identify and work through deep emotional and psychological conflicts that may be affecting the patient's physical well-being. Working with inner feelings can reduce chronic tension and improve the patient's overall well-being. Relaxation techniques help patients reduce stress levels and relax the body and mind, which helps improve cardiovascular function.

Progressive muscle relaxation (PMR) involves alternating tension and relaxation of different muscle groups in the body. It helps to reduce physical stress, improve blood circulation and normalise blood pressure, which is important for the prevention and treatment of hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases.

Breathing exercises, such as diaphragmatic breathing or the Buteyko method, aim to relax the body and improve the supply of oxygen to the tissues. They also help to reduce stress and improve cardiovascular function.

Effective stress management is important for the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular disease. There are various methods to help people cope with everyday stress and chronic worries.

Cognitive reappraisal techniques help patients change their attitudes toward stressful situations, reducing their perception of them as threatening. For example, instead of focusing on the stress, a person can focus on solving the problem or on what they can control about the situation. Group psychotherapy and support groups can

be helpful for people with CVD. Participation in such groups helps patients feel supported, reduce feelings of isolation, and learn to cope with the emotions associated with the disease. Social support reduces stress levels and improves overall well-being.

Regular physical activity is not only important for heart health, it is also an effective way to combat stress. It promotes the production of endorphins (happy hormones), improves mood and reduces anxiety and depression.

Yoga and Tai Chi combine physical activity with breathing exercises and meditation and help to reduce stress levels, improve flexibility and blood circulation, which has a positive effect on cardiovascular health.

A healthy diet and maintaining a normal weight are important aspects of CVD prevention and treatment. Psychosomatic approaches include educating patients about healthy eating habits and dealing with emotional overeating (overeating due to stress or depression). Advice may include developing healthy eating habits, controlling salt, sugar and fat intake, and supporting smoking and alcohol cessation.

In some cases, treatment of cardiovascular disease may include medication intervention to correct psycho-emotional state, such as antidepressants or anxiolytics. Psychotropic medications, especially when combined with psychotherapy and relaxation techniques, can effectively reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety, which in turn improves cardiovascular health.

Modern approaches to the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases, taking into account psychosomatic aspects, require a comprehensive approach that includes both traditional medical methods and psychotherapeutic interventions, relaxation and stress management techniques. Psychological health is important for maintaining the normal functioning of the cardiovascular system and working with the emotional and psycho-emotional aspects of patients' lives helps to improve their condition and reduce risks to cardiovascular health.

The study of psychosomatic mechanisms of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) is indeed an important step towards the development of comprehensive therapies aimed at improving patients' quality of life and reducing morbidity. Understanding how psychological and emotional factors influence the development and course of cardiovascular disease allows us to create more effective approaches to prevention and treatment that take into account not only physical but also psycho-emotional aspects of health.

There is a clear association between psychoemotional states and the development of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Stress, depression, anxiety, aggression and other emotional disorders can significantly affect physiological processes, leading to high blood pressure, development of atherosclerosis, heart and vascular dysfunction. Psychosomatic mechanisms play a key role in the development of hypertension, coronary heart disease, heart attacks and strokes.

Emotional tension, chronic stress and negative experiences activate the sympathetic nervous system and increase the level of stress hormones (adrenaline, cortisol), which increases the load on the heart and blood vessels. In turn, this increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. Psychological disorders also influence inflammatory processes that can accelerate the development of atherosclerosis and other vascular problems.

Understanding of psychosomatic aspects of diseases opens new horizons in the development of effective methods of treatment and prevention of CVD. Modern medicine increasingly recognises the importance of the psycho-emotional state of patients, so approaches to the treatment of CVDs should be comprehensive and include both traditional medical methods and psychotherapeutic interventions, relaxation techniques, stress management and cognitive-behavioural therapy, which allows not only to reduce the symptoms of diseases, but also to improve the quality of life of patients.

Psychotherapeutic interventions such as cognitive behavioural therapy, as well as relaxation and meditation techniques, have proven effective in reducing stress, anxiety and depression in patients with CVD. These techniques help to reduce psychological stress, improve general well-being, normalise blood pressure and improve cardiovascular health in general.

It is important to consider psychosomatic aspects in the prevention and early diagnosis of cardiovascular disease, which will not only prevent the development of disease but also improve the prognosis of patients who already have cardiovascular disease. Psycho-emotional well-being plays an important role in maintaining health and its improvement can significantly reduce morbidity.

Thus, psychosomatic aspects play an important role in the development and course of cardiovascular diseases. Understanding these mechanisms and integrating psychotherapeutic methods and relaxation techniques into the treatment and prevention of CVDs can significantly improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the risk of complications. An integrated approach that takes into account both physical and psycho-emotional

health is the key to successfully combating cardiovascular disease in the modern world.

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